

INFORMED CONSENT (PARENTS/CAREGIVERS)

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Title of Research Project: *Nudging Parents to Engage: An adaptation of an SMS-based educational engagement intervention for caregivers in Ghana*

Principal Investigator: Sharon Wolf

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Background and Purpose of Research

Findings from previous research have shown that children become very interested in school and do well in their academic work when their parents show interest and become actively involved in their education. However, whether or not parents will become actively involved in their children's education also partly depends on the parents' access to information and knowledge about school and the specific things they can do to support their children. This study will gather information that will help us to identify the issues that often prevent parents from becoming actively engaged in their children's education, and take suggestions from parents on how these issues can be overcome. The researchers have also developed a program to help motivate parents to actively engage in their children's education, including the education of their girl-child. This study will help the researchers to present this program to participants for them to share their views about whether or not the contents of the program align with their culture, examine whether the program will likely encourage parents to engage, take suggestions from parents to revise the program to make it more likely to inspire them (and other parents) to engage in their children's education, and to find out how best (i.e., in what medium) these messages can be communicated to parents.

Nature of Research

This study will be conducted in eight selected communities from the Northern, middle, and southern belts of Ghana, and will involve focus group discussions and semi-structured interviews by trained field staff. In all, about 160 adult residents living in the selected communities will be recruited to participate in this study. We invite you to take part in this study because you live in one of the selected communities where this research is being conducted. You fit the research because you are aged between 18 and 60 years old, and are a parent or caregiver of a school-going child who is aged between five and 15 years. You also fit the research because you speak the native dialect of the community and have resided in the community for at least two years.

Participants Involvement

After the study has been well explained to you and you have agreed to participate, we will guide you to either sign or thumb-print on a form to show that you have agreed to participate in this study. We will then schedule a day where you will meet with the other participants to decide on a day and time for the focus group discussions. We will hold two group discussions within a week, with each lasting about two hours. We will observe the discussions and take notes and/or record the discussions after all participants agree to it. After the focus group discussions, you may be selected for a face-to-face interview in a place in your home that offers privacy and quietness, where you will be interviewed to answer some further questions about the issues discussed in the focus group discussions. The interview will last for about 35 minutes. You will not be asked about information that can let people identify you, such as your name, telephone number, or your house address.

Possible Risks and Discomforts

The risk to you in this study is that you may become tired when participating in the focus group discussions or when answering the interview questions. The focus group discussions will be stopped after every hour for you to take some rest to prevent tiredness or take some snack that will be provided at the meetings. You may also experience some negative emotional reactions when listening and contributing to the focus group discussions or responding to the interview questions. In this unlikely event, you will be referred to a clinical psychologist or a community psychiatric nurse at the nearest hospital that same day for counselling support.

Possible Benefits

There are no direct benefits for participating in this study. Nonetheless, your participation could probably provide you with the opportunity to reflect on the issues that prevent you or other community members from actively engaging in the education of their children, including their female children.

The indirect benefits for participating are that your contribution will help researchers to understand the issues or challenges that hinder parents' effort from being actively involved in their children's education. Again, the information will help the researchers to revise the program they have developed in order to align with the cultural practices of your community, and possibly inspire parents in your community or similar settings to become more engaged in the school activities of their children.

Confidentiality

We will ensure that the information you provide will remain anonymous (i.e., in no way will your information be linked to your identity) by removing all your personal and identifiable information that could make others to be able to identify you before data is stored. The focus group discussions and interviews will be conducted in quiet, comfortable, and secluded places in your community and your own home, respectively, to ensure your privacy. Your results will be kept confidential (i.e., we assure you that we will protect the information we have about you) by storing electronic information on password protected devices that only the research team will have access to. Only the core members of the research team will be able to look at your findings. Information in hard copies (such as the consent forms) will be kept safely in a locked cabinet in one of the researcher's office in the College of Health Sciences at the University of Ghana. We will use the information from the study to revise the program, but in doing so, no identifying information of participants will ever be used in the revision or in the report that will be written after this study. **We will keep all the information for about six years after the end of the study before it will be permanently destroyed.**

Compensation

You will not be paid to take part in the study and there will be no costs involved for you, if you agree to take part in this study. However, as an appreciation for your time, you will be given a token of gift (either a bar of soap, a box of sugar, or two exercise books and pen/cils for your ward) after participating in the focus group discussions. You will also be offered snacks to refresh you at the meetings.

Additional Cost

There will be no additional costs to you when you participate in this study.

Voluntary Participation and Right to Leave the Research

Your participation in this study is voluntary and will not suffer any penalty for withdrawing at any time during the study.

Feedback to Participants

We will provide you with the results of this research by July 2022 when the study would have been completed with the program also revised, based on your contributions. The findings will be shared at a community forum or at a District Assembly meeting where you will be invited.

Funding Information

This study is supported financially by the LEGO Foundation.

Sharing of Participants' Information/Data

The information collected from you will not be shared with any other individual or organization. Only the Principal Investigators own the information that will be collected from you.

Provision of Information and Consent for participants

A copy of the information sheet and informed consent form will be given to you after it has been signed or

thumb-printed to keep. The discussions at the group meetings and the interviews will be recorded after all participants agree to it. However, at the group discussions and interview, you will not be asked about information that can let people identify you, such as your name, telephone number, or your house address.

Contacts for Additional Information

For additional information concerning this research you can contact:

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Richard Appiah; riappiah@ug.edu.gh; +233245823866

Elisabetta Aurino; e.aurino@ub.edu; +34 623 006 147

Your Rights as a Participant

Please note that your participation in this research is voluntary. You have the right to be informed about the study before, during, and after the study. You can also decide to leave the research without any penalties. This research has been reviewed and approved by the Ghana Health Service Ethics Review Committee (GHS-ERC). If you have any questions about your rights as a research participant you can contact the GHS-ERC Administrator on +233 503539896 or email address: ethics.research@ghsmail.org.

CONSENT FORM

STUDY TITLE: Nudging Parents to Engage: An adaptation of an SMS-based educational engagement intervention for caregivers in Ghana

PARTICIPANTS' STATEMENT

I acknowledge that I have read or have had the purpose and contents of the Participants' Information Sheet read and all questions satisfactorily explained to me in my native language. I fully understand the contents and any potential implications as well as my right to change my mind (i.e., withdraw from the research) even after I have signed this form.

I agree to the request that the interview be recorded without information about me that can be used to identify my identity:

Yes	
No	

I voluntarily agree to be part of this research.

Name of Participant.....

Participants' SignatureOR Thumb Print.....

Date:.....

INTERPRETERS' STATEMENT

I interpreted the purpose and contents of the Participants' Information Sheet to the afore named participant to the best of my ability in the participant's native language to his proper understanding.

All questions, appropriate clarifications sort by the participant and answers were also duly interpreted to his/her satisfaction.

Name of Interpreter/Independent Mediator.....

Signature of Interpreter..... OR Thumb Print

Date:..... Contact Details.....

STATEMENT OF WITNESS

I was present when the purpose and contents of the Participant Information Sheet was read and explained satisfactorily to the participant's native language.

I confirm that he/she was given the opportunity to ask questions/seek clarifications and same were duly answered to his/her satisfaction before voluntarily agreeing to be part of the research.

Name:.....

Signature..... OR Thumb Print

Date:.....

INVESTIGATOR STATEMENT AND SIGNATURE

I certify that the participant has been given ample time to read and learn about the study. All questions and clarifications raised by the participant have been addressed.

Researcher's name.....

Signature

Date.....

SEMI-INTERVIEW GUIDE

Demographic information: Please tell me about the following information about yourself.

<p>1. Gender:</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse; margin-bottom: 20px;"> <tr> <td style="width: 70%;">Male</td> <td style="width: 30%;">1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Female</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </table> <p>2. Age:</p> <p>Please what is your present age.....</p> <p>3. Educational Level:</p> <p>Please tell me about your current level of education.</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 70%;">None</td> <td style="width: 30%;">1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Primary</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Junior High Sch.</td> <td>3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Secondary</td> <td>4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tertiary</td> <td>5</td> </tr> </table>	Male	1	Female	2	None	1	Primary	2	Junior High Sch.	3	Secondary	4	Tertiary	5	<p>4. Marital status:</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse; margin-bottom: 20px;"> <tr> <td style="width: 70%;">Single</td> <td style="width: 30%;">1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Married</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Cohabiting</td> <td>3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Divorced/Separated</td> <td>4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Widowed</td> <td>5</td> </tr> </table> <p>5. Parenting/Caregiver status:</p> <p>How many children of school-going age are under your care, and how many are female?</p> <p>Total:</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse; margin-bottom: 20px;"> <tr> <td style="width: 70%;">Female</td> <td style="width: 30%;"></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Male</td> <td></td> </tr> </table> <p>6. Schooling of ward/s:</p> <p>Please how many of the children of school-going age under your care are currently attending school?</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p>	Single	1	Married	2	Cohabiting	3	Divorced/Separated	4	Widowed	5	Female		Male	
Male	1																												
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Interview schedule (Parents/Caregivers)

Preamble:

Researchers and educators have found that children whose parents or caregivers are actively engaged in their education tend to develop high interest in school and do well in their school activities. However, although parents may wish to be actively involved in the educational matters of their children (including their female children), a number of issues or factors may prevent them from doing so. In this first meeting, we will take turns to share our views on these issues and make suggestions to overcome them, where possible.

1. Are all or some of your children currently enrolled in school? What do you do, as their caregiver, to support their education? Why are some of your children not enrolled in school?
2. In your view, what is your main role as a caregiver in supporting your child education? Do you think your role is different based on the child gender or her/his age? In which ways?
3. What are some of the things you do to support your child's education? What are the issues or challenges that hinder your efforts (and the efforts of other parents in your community) from actively engaging in your child's education? Are your challenges different depending on whether the child is a boy or a girl? Or an adolescent boy or adolescent girls?
4. How does each of these issues or challenges specifically interrupt with your efforts to become actively engaged in the education of your children?
5. What information or strategies can support you or parents from your community to overcome each of these identified issues/challenges? Do you think teachers or other figures in your communities could support your engagement and overcoming these barriers? If yes, what can they do to support?
6. What messages, in your view, can inspire you or parents in your community to become actively involved in their children's education?
7. How do you think these messages should be crafted to make them more helpful to you?
8. Do you have any other suggestions on how the education of your children/boys/girls can be supported?